

Study code: 19/263

Laboratory bioassay to determine the efficacy of trap and bait products against American cockroaches, *Periplaneta americana* and German cockroaches, *Blattella germanica*

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September 2019

Draft Report

✓ **Chemicals Regulation
Directorate Certificated**
✓ **GLP Compliant**

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Certification

This report represents a true and accurate record of all data obtained.

Signed..... Sean Loakes Date 9th September 2019
Sean Loakes
Study Director

Approved by..... [Signature] Date 9/9/19
Richard Kinsey
Facility Management

All raw data and a copy of the final report will be archived at i2LResearch for a period of ten years. At the end of this period all data relating to this report will either be retained by i2LResearch for a further disclosed period of time at an extra cost, destroyed at the sponsor's request or passed on to the sponsor at the sponsor's expense.

Report circulated to: Domobios (1 copy)
i2LResearch Ltd (1 copy)

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Study Information

- i. Title of study:** Laboratory bioassay to determine the efficacy of trap and bait products against American cockroaches, *Periplaneta americana* and German cockroaches, *Blattella germanica*
- ii. Testing facility:** *i2L*Research Ltd
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- iv. *i2L*Research Ltd Study code:** 19/263
- v. Study start date:** 17th July 2019
Experimental start date: 29th July 2019
Experimental end date: 25th August 2019
Study end date: 9th September 2019
- vi. Study Director:** Sean Loakes
vii. Primary personnel: Lewis Middleton
viii. Certification: ORETO Number 418

ix. Test items:

Test item	Batch/ Lot number	CAS Registry №/ EPA №	Physical description of test substance	Storage conditions	Expiry date	<i>i2L</i> Research code number
Domobios trap	N/a	N/a	Black plastic sticky trap with clear bottom.	Ambient	N/a	19072903 - 19072911
roach killing bait	232181	67485-29-4 / 64240-2	Small square plastic tray	Ambient	29.07.21*	19072912 - 19072917
MAX roach killing bait	17872	120068-37-3 / 64240-34	Large square plastic tray	Ambient	29.07.21*	19072918 - 19072921

**i2L*Research Ltd default expiry date.

Summary

A series of behavioural bioassays were performed under controlled laboratory conditions in order to compare the efficacy of one trap and one insecticidal bait product against American cockroaches (*Periplaneta americana*) and German cockroaches, (*Blattella germanica*), in terms of numbers caught or incapacitated (knocked down or dead), in a 1m² arena over a 72-hour experimental period.

Bioassays were conducted within plastic arenas. 20 cockroaches (2 adult males, 2 adult females and 16 mixed stage nymphs) were introduced into each test arena which included one of the products to be evaluated. The number of cockroaches caught in the trap/ knocked down/dead was assessed over 72 hours.

Domobios trap. Application of the Domobios trap resulted in 93.4% German cockroaches and 93.6% American cockroaches trapped at 24 hours post exposure. At 72 hours, 100% of German cockroaches were trapped with 93.6% American cockroaches trapped.

Insecticidal Bait. Application of insecticidal bait stations against German cockroaches resulted in 71.3% affected (unrecovered/moribund or dead) cockroaches at 72 hours post exposure to the product. Application of Combat insecticidal bait stations against American cockroaches, resulted in 67.5% affected cockroaches at 72 hours post exposure to the product.

In conclusion, over a 72 hour experimental period, the level of trapping success resultant from application of the Domobios trap was higher than the level of knockdown and mortality associated with application of the insecticidal bait. It would be a fair statement to claim that in a resistant genotype (as opposed to the insecticide-sensitive strains used in this study) the level of efficacy in the insecticidal bait may be expected to decline, whereas application of the Domobios trap would remain similarly effective.

Aim

A series of behavioural bioassays were performed under controlled laboratory conditions in order to compare the efficacy of one trap and one insecticidal bait product against American cockroaches (*Periplaneta americana*) and German cockroaches, (*Blattella germanica*), in terms of numbers caught, in a 1m² arena over a 72-hour experimental period.

Methodology

Test species. American cockroaches, *Periplaneta americana*, and German cockroaches, *Blattella germanica*, were both obtained from a laboratory culture maintained at *i2L*Research (Cardiff, UK), they have been in culture for over 20 years. Test populations of both species of cockroaches were established in separate holding tanks before the start of the study as follows; 2 adult males, 2 adult females and 16 mixed instar nymphs (3rd-5th instar).

Test treatments and application. One monitoring trap (Domobios trap) was assessed, provided by the sponsor. In addition, one insecticidal bait, applicable to each cockroach species, was tested under similar conditions; (1) American cockroaches: treated with roach killing bait, presented as a bait station and containing Fipronil 0.03% per 1g of bait material (2) German cockroaches: treated with roach killing bait, presented as a bait station and containing Hydramethylnon 2% per 1g of bait material. Combat insecticidal bait). The trap/insecticidal bait station was assessed immediately after opening and placed in the test arena according to the sponsor's instructions (Figure 1). An untreated control was also included in order to validate batch fitness of the insects.

Test arena. Experiments were conducted in arenas, measuring approximately 1 m long x 1 m wide. The vertical walls of each arena were coated in Fluon (liquid PTFE) (to prevent insects from escaping). The floor of each arena was lined with white paper. To prevent interference between replicates, one arena *per* test chamber was evaluated at a time. A harbourage (a shelter taken from the holding

tanks) containing cockroaches was introduced into one corner of the arena and the trap under evaluation in the opposite corner to the harbourage. A food source (bran pellets) and a water source (moistened cotton pads presented on a petri dish) were placed in the centre of the arena.

Figure 1. Schematic of arena set up with the relative position of introduced materials.

Experimental design. Each replicate of the trial was initiated 1 hour before the lights were turned off for the night, to simulate the behaviour of the cockroaches during the night when they are actively foraging. A test population of twenty cockroaches (as described above) was established on a harbourage, which was subsequently placed in one side of the arena. Cockroaches were allowed 1 hour to acclimatise. Following this period, the trap/insecticidal bait unit to be assessed was placed at the opposite end of the arena (Figure 1). The position of the trap/insecticidal bait unit was rotated between arena ends for each new replicate, to prevent any positional bias. Food (laboratory rodent bran diet) and water (90mm petri dish with moistened cotton pads) and an alternative harbourage item was provided at the opposite end of the arena to the position of the test item.

Assessments. Trap unit; at approximately 24 hours, the number of cockroaches inside the trap was counted. Further assessments at 48 and 72 hours were undertaken.

Insecticidal bait unit; at approximately 24, 48 and 72 hours, the number of knocked down, moribund and dead insects was recorded.

Replication. Four (4) replicates were conducted for each treatment condition (3), for each species (2) giving a total of 24 tests.

Environmental conditions. Temperature was maintained between 27.9 and 33.4°C and relative humidity between 33.3 and 59.8% throughout the experimental period.

Statistical analyses. Percentage mean number trapped and standard error values were calculated, and results are presented in a tabular and graphical format. No further statistical analysis was deemed necessary by the Study Director.

Protocol amendments/deviations. The study protocol is included in Appendix II. There were no protocol amendments issued during the execution of the study.

Results and Conclusions

The raw data is included in Appendix I of this report. The calculated percentage means are summarised in Tables 1-2 and Figures 2-3 below.

Domobios trap. Application of the Domobios trap resulted in 93.4% German cockroaches and 93.6% American cockroaches at 24 hours post exposure. At 72 hours, 100% of German cockroaches were trapped with 93.6% American cockroaches trapped.

In conclusion, the Domobios trap was highly effective in terms of delivering a rapid catch rate of a significant percentage of the cockroach test population (both species).

Table 1. Percentage trapped German and American cockroaches following exposure to **Domobios trap** over a 72 hour experimental period (**means** ± standard errors, n=4)

Time post exposure	German cockroaches			American cockroaches		
	Adults in trap	Nymphs in trap	Total population (Adults & Nymphs)	Adults in trap	Nymphs in trap	Total population (Adults & Nymphs)
24 hrs	93.8	93.3	93.4	100.0	91.9	93.6
	± 6.3	± 4.7	± 5.0	± 0.0	± 4.9	± 3.9
48 hrs	100.0	98.3	98.7	100.0	93.6	94.9
	± 0.0	± 1.7	± 1.3	± 0.0	± 2.6	± 2.0
72 hrs	100.0	100.0	100.0	93.8	93.4	93.6
	± 0.0	± 0.0	± 0.0	± 6.3	± 4.7	± 3.3

Insecticidal Bait. Application of insecticidal bait stations against German cockroaches resulted in 71.3% affected (unrecovered/moribund or dead) cockroaches at 72 hours post exposure to the product. Application of insecticidal bait stations against American cockroaches, resulted in 67.5% affected (unrecovered/moribund or dead) cockroaches at 72 hours post exposure to the product. Control mortality in German cockroaches was 18.8% at 72 hours, this high number is likely due to larger nymph and adult cockroaches cannibalising on the smaller nymphs included in the test population. Control mortality in American cockroaches was 6.3% at 72 hours.

Table 1. Percentage affected (KD, moribund and dead) German and American cockroaches following exposure to insecticidal bait variants over a 72 hour experimental period (means \pm standard errors, n=4)

German cockroaches										
Treatment	Assessment time	Adults				Nymphs				Total population (Adults & Nymphs)
		KD	M	D	KD+M+D	KD	M	D	KD+M+D	KD+M+D
	24 hr	11.3	22.5	0.0	33.8	10.9	4.7	10.9	26.6	28.8
		± 6.6	± 13.1	± 0.0	± 13.4	± 5.3	± 3.0	± 3.0	± 6.4	± 8.3
	48 hr	28.8	23.8	16.3	68.8	14.1	15.6	29.7	59.4	62.5
		± 10.9	± 10.3	± 9.9	± 12.0	± 12.1	± 7.4	± 9.0	± 4.0	± 3.2
	72 hr	18.8	12.5	68.8	100.0	0.0	15.6	46.9	62.5	71.3
		± 12.0	± 12.5	± 12.0	± 0.0	± 0.0	± 9.4	± 9.0	± 4.4	± 2.4
Treatment	Assessment time	KD	M	D	KD+M+D	KD	M	D	KD+M+D	KD+M+D
Untreated control	24 hr	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.6	1.6	3.1	2.5
		± 0.0	± 1.6	± 1.6	± 1.8	± 1.4				
	48 hr	0.0	0.0	6.3	6.3	0.0	1.6	3.1	4.7	5.0
		± 0.0	± 0.0	± 6.3	± 6.3	± 0.0	± 1.6	± 1.8	± 1.6	± 2.0
	72 hr	0.0	0.0	18.8	18.8	0.0	1.6	6.3	7.8	10.0
		± 0.0	± 0.0	± 6.3	± 6.3	± 0.0	± 1.6	± 2.6	± 3.0	± 2.0
American cockroaches										
Treatment	Assessment time	Adults				Nymphs				Total population (Adults & Nymphs)
		KD	M	D	KD+M+D	KD	M	D	KD+M+D	KD+M+D
	24 hr	12.5	50.0	0.0	62.5	23.4	7.8	0.0	31.3	37.5
		± 12.5	± 22.8	± 0.0	± 16.1	± 6.4	± 4.7	± 0.0	± 8.1	6.6
	48 hr	18.8	56.3	6.3	81.3	14.1	28.1	7.8	50.0	56.3
		± 12.0	± 21.3	± 6.3	± 12.0	± 8.2	± 9.7	± 4.7	± 10.5	8.5
	72 hr	6.3	50.0	31.3	87.5	14.1	32.8	15.6	62.5	67.5
		± 6.3	± 17.7	± 18.8	± 12.5	± 9.0	± 10.6	± 4.0	± 11.7	9.7
Treatment	Assessment time	KD	M	D	KD+M+D	KD	M	D	KD+M+D	KD+M+D
Untreated control	24 hr	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
		± 0.0	± 0.0	0.0	0.0					
	48 hr	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
		± 0.0	± 0.0	0.0	0.0					
	72 hr	0.0	0.0	6.3	6.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
		± 0.0	± 0.0	± 6.3	± 6.3	± 0.0	± 0.0	± 0.0	0.0	1.3

Figure 2. Percentage trapped German and American cockroaches following exposure to Domobios trap over a 72 hour experimental period (means \pm standard errors, n=4)

Figure 3. Percentage affected (KD, moribund and dead) German and American cockroaches (nymph and adults combined) following exposure to insecticidal bait variants over a 72 hour experimental period (means \pm standard errors, n=4)

Appendix I Raw data

(All replicates out of 20 cockroaches (2 males, 2 females and 16 mixed stage nymphs) unless otherwise stated)

German cockroaches

Replicate	Treatment:		Dombios trap	
	Assessment time	Adults in trap	Nymphs in trap	Total population (Adults & Nymphs)
Rep 1	24 hr	4	15*	19
	48 hr	4	14*	18
	72 hr	4	15*	19
Rep 2	24 hr	3	12	15
	48 hr	4	15	19
	72 hr	4	15	19
Rep 3	24 hr	4	14	18
	48 hr	4	15	19
	72 hr	4	15	19
Rep 4	24 hr	4	16	20
	48 hr	4	16	20
	72 hr	4	16	20

*out of 15 nymphs

Treatment:		bait										
Replicate	Assessment time	Adults					Nymphs					Total population (Adults & Nymphs) KD+M+D
		KD	M	D	KD+M+D	KD	M	D	KD+M+D			
Rep 1	24 hr	1	0	0	1	1	2	1	4			5
	48 hr	1	1	1	3	0	4	7	11			14
	72 hr	1	0	3	4	0	0	11	11			15
Rep 2	24 hr	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	2			2
	48 hr	2	0	0	2	8	1	1	10			12
	72 hr	2	0	2	4	0	6	4	10			14
Rep 3	24 hr	0	2	0	2	2	0	2	4			6
	48 hr	0	2	0	2	0	5	4	9			11
	72 hr	0	2	2	4	0	4	7	11			15
Rep 4	24 hr	1	2	0	3	4	0	3	7			10
	48 hr	2	1	2	5	1	0	7	8			13
	72 hr	0	0	5	5	0	0	8	8			13

Treatment:		Untreated control										Total population (Adults & Nymphs) KD+M+D
Replicate	Assessment time	Adults				Nymphs				KD+M+D		
		KD	M	D	KD+M+D	KD	M	D	KD+M+D			
Rep 1	24 hr	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	
	48 hr	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	
	72 hr	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	2	2	
Rep 2	24 hr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	48 hr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	72 hr	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	
Rep 3	24 hr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	48 hr	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	2	
	72 hr	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	2	
Rep 4	24 hr	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	
	48 hr	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	
	72 hr	0	0	1	1	0	0	2	2	2	3	

American cockroaches

Treatment:		Domobios trap		
Replicate	Assessment time	Adults in trap	Nymphs in trap	Total population (Adults & Nymphs)
Rep 1	24 hr	4	15*	19
	48 hr	4	15*	19
	72 hr	4	15*	19
Rep 2	24 hr	4	12	16
	48 hr	4	14	18
	72 hr	4	12	16
Rep 3	24 hr	4	16	20
	48 hr	4	15	19
	72 hr	3	16	19
Rep 4	24 hr	4	14	18
	48 hr	4	14	18
	72 hr	4	15	19

*out of 15 nymphs

Treatment:		bait										Total population (Adults & Nymphs) KD+M+D
Replicate	Assessment time	Adults				Nymphs						
		KD	M	D	KD+M+D	KD	M	D	KD+M+D			
Rep 1	24 hr	0	4	0	4	6	0	0	6			
	48 hr	0	4	0	4	0	9	3	12			
Rep 2	72 hr	0	2	2	4	0	10	4	14			
	24 hr	0	1	0	1	5	3	0	8			
Rep 3	48 hr	2	0	0	2	6	3	0	9			
	72 hr	1	1	0	2	6	2	2	10			
Rep 4	24 hr	2	0	0	2	2	0	0	2			
	48 hr	1	3	0	4	2	2	0	4			
Rep 4	72 hr	0	4	0	4	0	4	1	5			
	48 hr	0	3	0	3	2	2	0	4			
	72 hr	0	2	1	3	1	4	2	7			
		0	1	3	4	3	5	3	11			
										15		

Treatment:		Untreated control									
Replicate	Assessment time	Adults				Nymphs				Total population (Adults & Nymphs) KD+M+D	
		KD	M	D	KD+M+D	KD	M	D	KD+M+D		
Rep 1	24 hr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	48 hr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	72 hr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Rep 2	24 hr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	48 hr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	72 hr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Rep 3	24 hr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	48 hr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	72 hr	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	
Rep 4	24 hr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	48 hr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	72 hr	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Study code: 19/263

Study Information

Study title: Laboratory bioassay to determine the efficacy of trap and bait products against American cockroaches, *Periplaneta americana* and German cockroaches, *Blattella germanica*

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Tel. 0044 02922 400 587

Proposal submitted: 17th July 2019

Objective. A laboratory bioassay is required to assess the efficacy of trap and bait products against American cockroaches, *Periplaneta americana* and German cockroaches, *Blattella germanica* in terms of total catch rates *per* unit over a defined period of time.

Test systems. American cockroaches, *Periplaneta americana* and German cockroaches, *Blattella germanica*, will be obtained from a specified laboratory culture. Mixed age and sex adult cockroaches will be used in the experiments (2 adult males: 2 adult females (non-gravid): 16 mixed stage nymph will constitute a test population *per* replicate test.

Test treatments and application. One monitoring trap (Domobios trap) will be assessed provided by the sponsor. In addition, one insecticidal bait unit (Combat) will be assessed under similar test conditions. There is one rate applicable to each cockroach species under evaluation (i.e. 1 rate for small cockroaches and 1 rate for large cockroaches). The trap/insecticidal bait station will be assessed immediately after opening and placed in the test arena according to the sponsor's instructions. An untreated control will be included in order to validate batch fitness of the insects.

Test arena. Experiments will be conducted in arenas, each measuring approximately 1 m long x 1 m wide. The sides of the arenas will be coated in Fluon (liquid PTFE) to prevent the insects from escaping, and the floor of the arena will be lined with white paper. Temperature and relative humidity will be monitored throughout the trial. The airflow will be turned off for the duration of the experiments. Lighting will be dimmed to encourage activity, and set at a 18:6, light:dark photoperiod. One arena will be placed in one chamber to prevent any interference between replicates.

Experimental design. The trial will commence an hour before the lights are due to be turned off for the night, to simulate the behaviour of the cockroaches during the night when they are foraging. Twenty cockroaches (as described above) will be established on a harbourage, which will then be placed in one side of the arena. Cockroaches will be left there for 1 hour to acclimatise. Following this period, the trap/insecticidal bait unit to be assessed will be placed at the opposite end of the arena (or in other location in consultation with the sponsor). The position of the trap/insecticidal bait unit will be rotated between arena ends for each new replicate, to prevent any positional bias. Food

(laboratory rodent bran diet) and water (90mm petri dish with moistened cotton pads) and an alternative harbourage item will be provided at the opposite end of the arena to the position of the test item. Pictures of the experiments and results will be included in the final report.

Assessments. Trap unit; at approximately 24 hours, the number of cockroaches inside the trap will be counted. Further assessments at 48 and 72 hours will be undertaken.

Insecticidal bait unit; at approximately 24, 48 and 72 hours, the number of knocked down, moribund and dead insects will be recorded.

Four (4) replicates will be conducted for each test item and control (3), for each species (2), giving a total of 24 tests to undertake.

Statistical analyses. Results will be presented in a tabular format. Analyses will be performed by the Study Director and will depend on the outcome of the testing at the discretion of the Study Director. Statistical analyses performed will be fully documented in the report.

Protocol amendments and deviations. Any protocol amendments and/or deviations will be documented, fully justified and maintained with the protocol. All protocol amendments will be approved by the sponsor and documented.

Archiving records. The original raw data, final report and any amendments will be archived at i2LResearch for a period of ten years. Following this ten year period the study file will either be destroyed at the sponsor's request, kept for a further period at an extra cost, or returned to the sponsor at the sponsor's expense. The final report, including any protocol amendments or deviations, will be forwarded to the Sponsor. Any unused test substances will be either be returned to the sponsor or disposed of with the sponsor's consent.

Health and Safety. The sponsor must supply full safety information with any materials, e.g. material safety data sheets. Usage of all products received from the sponsor will comply with company COSHH Risk Assessments according to i2LResearch Health and Safety requirements.

Appendix III

ORETO Certification

Certificate of

Official Recognition of Efficacy Testing Facilities or Organisations in the United Kingdom

This certifies that

I2LResearch Ltd

complies with the minimum standards laid down in
Regulation (EC) 1107/2009 for efficacy testing.

The above Facility/Organisation has been officially
recognised as being competent to carry out efficacy trials/tests
in the United Kingdom in the following categories:

**Agriculture/Horticulture
Biologicals and Semiochemicals
Stored Crops**

Date of issue: 11 March 2019
Effective date: 1 January 2019
Expiry date: 31 December 2023

Signature

Authorised signatory

Certification Number

ORETO 418

Chemicals Regulation Division

Department of
**Agriculture and
Rural Development**